

DEVELOPING PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS' INTEREST IN LEARNING

Kudyarova Artikgul

Student of the Faculty of primary education of
The Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after
Ajiniyaz

Abstract. This article talks about the methods of increasing interest in learning among elementary school students. Raising the young generation as a well-rounded person is one of the urgent issues facing our society. They are the people who leave a free and prosperous Motherland to the next generations and create the great future of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: primary, method, class, pedagogue, psychology, knowledge, formation.

INTRODUCTION

The quality and effectiveness of the educational process increases only when a conscious desire for knowledge is formed. If the initial learning process does not create a desire to learn in the student, his desire to learn will gradually decrease in the upper grades. So, how to awaken a conscious desire to learn, independent and critical thinking in the hearts of students?

METHODS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

For this reason, lessons can be learned from the exemplary lives of our great grandfathers, who are still recognized by the world even after centuries. How did our great thinkers achieve such high results? For what? Is it our grandfather Alisher Navoi, the Sultan of Soz, or our grandfather Abu Ali ibn Sina, who became famous in European countries under the name of Avicenna? If we look at history to find answers to these questions, then we can witness that their parents noticed in time that they were interested in learning science from childhood. We can cite as an example that our grandfather Alisher Navoi memorized Farididdin Attar's Mantiq

ut-Tayr when he was 4-5 years old. The life scenes of the youth of our great ancestors are included in multimedia applications in the form of cartoons, and in accordance with the theme of each lesson, at least one of the childhood events of the great thinkers are shown in spiritual moments, and the students are motivated to achieve such high results. shooting and the solution to this is only and only to get deep knowledge and it is necessary to organize a lesson with the goal of achieving great goals as a result of the knowledge gained in the future and unceasing efforts.

RESULTS

One of the main tasks of primary education is to ensure that students acquire the knowledge, skills and qualifications specified in the state educational standards based on the competency approach in each subject. in the process of acquisition, it is formed under the guidance of the teacher and develops regularly. That is why educational games based on modern pedagogical technology such as What is good and what is bad?, Puzzle market, Box of Virtues, Plant one, plant ten should be widely used in the course of the lesson. As a result of such educational activities, students who have graduated from primary education should understand that the objective world consists of animate and inanimate nature, and people live and work in a certain society, and have clear concepts and ideas about nature and society. Because it is impossible to form students as individuals and adapt them to social life without understanding this fact.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The saying that education begins with a textbook applies especially to elementary education. Textbook plays an important role in the educational process. It is known that etiquette lessons have a special place in the formation of cultural and aesthetic feelings based on national values in the hearts of students. Here, before talking about the 1st grade etiquette textbooks, I would like to quote the following opinion of M. I. Makhmudov: "It is difficult for the teachers of the present time to introduce the problematic method. Because textbooks and educational programs are

based on outdated didactics and methodology based on traditional pedagogical thinking. The logic of explaining the educational material requires a detailed explanation, and the independent creative activities of the students are not taken into account. Based on this, I would like to make the following suggestions regarding etiquette textbooks. Taking into account the age characteristics of the 1st grade students, cartoons reflecting the subject of the lesson are shown, a problematic situation is created about the virtues of the heroes, why they have fallen into such situations, and etiquette that encourages students to think freely and draw conclusions. If textbooks and multimedia applications were created for their classes, it would have a positive effect on the education and creative thinking of students.

Unfortunately, in some families, after dinner, they usually sit together and watch various series that are not suitable for the children's age. Isn't it possible to talk about today's summary together? Is it possible to ask what their children have done, what achievements they have achieved, and the reason for their 4 or 3 grades? Also, it is extremely important for parents to check and monitor their children's homework and to be close to it. Because homework assignments are children's independent tasks, this is a process that encourages them to develop their level of thinking, ensure their activity, and work on themselves. In this regard, parents should not do their homework without the children's participation, but guide them educationally and give them directions for independent thinking. We will consider some ways to positively solve these problematic issues.

CONCLUSIONS

In a word, teachers cannot ensure children's well-being without the active support of parents. In this case, the teacher himself should be experienced, knowledgeable and educated in terms of pedagogy, psychology and physiology. That's the only way he can form independent thinking, active, initiative, intelligent, innovative, sensitive and intellectual abilities in children in cooperation with parents who are extremely demanding of him. For this, it is necessary to organize an Open

Day for parents once a week. In the process of observing these lessons, parents witness their children's mastery of subjects and their activity in lessons compared to their peers. As a result, parents pay more attention to their children so that they do not become ashamed of learning subjects among their classmates, and as a result of this, they do not become shy and free learners who find it difficult to freely express their thoughts.

REFERENCES

1. ЕРМАТОВА, Р. О. (2018). УПРАВЛЕНИЕ ВРЕМЕННЫМ УЧЕНИЕМ ДЛЯ СТУДЕНТОВ С ОБУЧЕНИЕМ ИНВАЛИДЫ. *Наука среди нас*, (7), 85-88.
2. Ermatova, R. O. (2018). ADVANTAGES OF THE TECHNIQUE "WHAT/HOW/WHY OUTLINES" IN DEVELOPING PRODUCTIVE SKILLS OF THE MEDICAL STUDENTS. *Актуальные проблемы гуманитарных и естественных наук*, (6), 69-71.
3. Utegenova, S., & Rozumova, D. (2024). DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING TAX AUDIT. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(6).
4. Utegenova, S., & Mirzabaeva, U. (2024). TODAY'S IMPORTANCE AND PROSPECTS OF AUDIT ACTIVITIES IN UZBEKISTAN. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 4(6), 93-95.
5. Utegenova, S., & Oralbaeva, F. (2024). O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotiga xorijiy investitsiyalar oqimini oshirishda mamlakatning investitsion muhiti jozibadorligini oshirish. *Журнал академических исследований нового Узбекистана*, 1(6), 131-134.
6. Khasanova, S., Akisheva, N., & Zholayeva, M. (2023). Methodological aspects of tax planning in the context of sustainable development. *Revista Gestão & Tecnologia*, 23(3), 286-298.
7. Маматкулов, Б. М., & Нематов, А. А. (2021). Ўзбекистон Республикаси аҳолиси орасида COVID-19 тарқалишининг хусусиятлари.

8. Abdullayeva, N. (2023). AHMAD YASSAWI SECT: THE ISSUE OF ZIKR AND THE STATUS OF ZAKIR. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(5), 438-440.
9. Bazarov, S. (2024). JURNALIST VA BLOGERLAR NUTQI ETIKASI. *Инновационные исследования в современном мире: теория и практика*, 3(1), 36-39.
10. Norqulovich, S. H. (2023, October). NURILLO CHORINING BADIY ASARLARIDA MILLIY KOLORITGA XOS KO ‘RINISHLAR NUTQIY JIHATDAN IFODALANISHI. In *International conference on multidisciplinary science* (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 25-29).
11. Ziyodullayeva, M., & Muxtorova, M. (2024). ABDULLA QODIRIY HAYOTI VA IJODIGA AYRIM CHIZGILAR. *NRJ*, 1(3), 860-863.
12. Muxtorova, M. (2024). MAXTUMQULI SHE’RIYATIDA AYTISHUV: AN’ANA VA IZDOSHLIK. *NRJ*, 1(3), 254-257.
13. Tajenova, G., Turdiyeva, G., Qurbanov, A., & Isakov, I. (2020). Current state and development of agricultural products exports of the Republic of Uzbekistan. *Архив научных исследований*, (14).
14. Janabay, I., Gulbahar, T., Gulayda, T., Alisher, Q., & Ilkhambek, I. (2020). Current state and development of agricultural products exports of the republic of uzbekistan. *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24(8), 1684-1693.
15. Turdieva, G., Abishov, M., & Muratbaev, I. (2024). THE IMPACT OF CREDIT RISKS ON AN EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION IN THE FINANCIAL SERVICES OF COMMERCIAL BANKS. *NRJ*, 1(4), 215-225.
16. Beglenov, N., & Muratbaev, I. (2023). HOTEL SERVICES AS AN OBJECT OF STRATEGIC MARKETING ORIENTED TO THE CONSUMER. *Science and Education in Karakalpakstan*, 32(2), 175-177.
17. Xalmuratovich, B. S. (2024). JAHON AMALIYOTIDA AGROKLASTER TIZIMINI SAMARALI TASHKIL ETISH VA YURITISH BO ‘YICHA TO

- ‘PLANGAN TAJRIBALAR TAHLILI. *Scientific Journal of Actuarial Finance and Accounting*, 4(04), 140-150.
18. Bayjanov, S. X., & Abishov, M. S. (2024). DEVELOPING THE ACTIVITY OF JOINT STOCK COMPANIES BY IMPROVING DIVIDEND POLICY. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 3(3), 94-97.
19. Sultanov, B., Nurimbetov, T., Bayjanov, S., Seyilbekov, B., & Durmanov, A. (2023, October). Trends in change and the current state of the effectiveness of land reclamation measures in agriculture. In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 2921, No. 1). AIP Publishing.
20. Байжанов, С. Х. (2023). ВНЕДРЕНИЕ ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИИ В СЕЛЬСКОЕ ХОЗЯЙСТВО НОВОГО УЗБЕКИСТАНА. *BOSHQARUV VA ETIKA QOIDALARI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 3(4), 51-53.
21. Омоновна, Е. Р. (2023). KLINIK ATAMALAR SHAKLLANTIRISHDA SUFFIKSATSIYA USULI VA TA ‘LIM TEXNOLOGIYALARI. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 9(3), 198-204.
22. Shodiyeva, G. (2024). O ‘ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILIDA SO ‘ZLARNI TURKUMLARGA AJRATISH MASALALARI. *Interpretation and researches*, (4 (26)).
23. qizi Tursunova, M. A., & qizi Shodieva, G. N. (2023). MAIN INFLUENTIAL FACTORS TO LANGUAGE LEARNING PROCESS. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(3 SPECIAL), 1181-1183.
24. Aliyeva, N., & qizi Shodiyeva, G. N. (2023). Ingliz Tilida So ‘Z Turkumlari Tasnifi Masalalari Sharhi. *Scholar*, 1(13), 22-27.
25. Navruza, A. (2023). INGLIZ TILI MORFOLOGIYASIDA SOZ TURKUMLARINI ORGANISH ZARURIYATI. *ITALY" ACTUAL PROBLEMS OF SCIENCE AND EDUCATION IN THE FACE OF MODERN CHALLENGES"*, 14(1).